

The Role of Perception of Gender Inequality, Self-discipline, and Social Responsibility in Predicting the Academic Achievement of Female Students in Tehran Universities

Mahboobeh Moosivand*1 Mohammad Javad Bagian Koulemarzi

1. Assistant Professor of Women Research Center, AL Zahra University, Tehran, Iran

2. Ph.D. in General Psychology

Abstract Introduction: It is necessary to study the social responsibility and self-discipline of the young generation because of their importance in determining the active force and future makers of society. Therefore, the main purpose of this study was the role of perception of gender inequality, self-discipline, and social responsibility in predicting the academic achievement of female students in Tehran universities. **Method:** This research is a descriptive correlational study based on the applied purpose and based on the data collection method. The statistical population of this study was all female students at Tehran universities in the academic year 1397-98. The research sample was 384 female students at the University of Tehran who were selected in multi-stage clusters. For data collection, the questionnaire of perception of gender inequality Khosrow et al., Zand Karimi self-disciplinary questionnaire, and Soroush responsibility questionnaire were used. The collected data were statistically analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient and multivariate regression. **Results:** The results of the correlation coefficient showed that there is a positive relationship between the perception of gender inequality, self-discipline, and responsibility with the academic achievement of female students ($P \geq 0.01$). The results of stepwise multivariate regression showed that 35% of the variance of female students' academic achievement is explained by perceptions of gender inequality, self-discipline, and responsibility. **Conclusion:** planning more quantitative and qualitative studies to promote the academic achievement of female students, considering their gender, social, cultural-educational, political, and economic role in society, is recommended. **Keywords:** Perception of Gender Inequality, Self-Discipline, Social Responsibility, Academic Achievement, Students.